

Landform Classification Using Hydrological Knowledge derived from Digital Elevation Models

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Abstract—Landforms are a fundamental component of physical geography, forming the basis of the Earth’s surface system. Accurate landform classification is crucial for geomorphological research and has significant implications for related studies. In this study, we extracted hydrologically constrained landform units from digital elevation models, which served as the foundational objects for classification. A deep learning method was applied to classify loess landforms, while geomorphic rule-based methods were used to classify karst landforms. The classification accuracies of loess and karst landforms were assessed by visual interpretation. The results show that karst landform classification achieved 94.44% accuracy, while loess classification reached 82.86%. These findings highlight the effectiveness of incorporating geomorphic semantics into landform units for accurately classifying different landforms, providing valuable insights for landform classification studies.

I. INTRODUCTION

Landforms are a fundamental component of physical geography and form the foundation of the Earth’s surface system [1-4]. Accurate landform classification is a core task of geomorphological research and has significant implications for understanding landform formation mechanisms [5], geomorphic dynamic processes [6] and soil erosion management [7]. However, the complex morphological characteristics of Earth’s surface, was shaped by various internal and external forces [8], making it challenging to delineate landform boundaries. Therefore, a method that can effectively classify landforms has profound value for geomorphological studies.

II. STUDY AREAS AND DATA

A. Study areas

The Loess Plateau spans approximately 291,890 km^2 . Its complex surface morphology and severe soil erosion [9] have

made it a key area for geomorphological research. Typical landforms include loess tablelands, ridges, hills, and gullies [10].

Figure 1. Study area of loess and karst landform. (a) Study of loess landform; (b) Study area of karst landform; (c) Loess tableland; (d) Loess ridge; (e) Loess hill; (f) Loess gully; (g) Karst Fenglin; (h) Karst Fengcong

The karst region in Guilin covers about 486 km^2 and is characterized by tropical and subtropical karst landforms such as Fenglin, Fengcong, depressions, and basins.

B. Data

For landform classification in both karst and loess regions, we utilized the Forest and Buildings Removed Copernicus DEM (FABDEM) as the primary data source. FABDEM, with a spatial resolution of 30 m, employs a random forest regression model to remove vegetation and building height biases, offering precise surface elevation data ideal for landform studies [11].

For the Loess Plateau, high-resolution remote sensing imagery (9.5 m) from Google Earth was used to reflect topographic texture, aiding in the classification of loess landforms. Additionally, stony mountain areas with minimal loess cover were identified, and the Guanzhong Basin boundary was manually delineated based on terrain conditions. These comprehensive datasets supported robust landform classification in the study regions.

III. METHODS

In this paper, we extracted hydrological knowledge from DEM, which served as a constraint in the form of landform units for classifying loess and karst landforms. The proposed method consists of four main components: (1) Binary terrain segmentation; (2) Hydrological constrained landform units extraction; (3) Karst landform unit classification using geomorphic; (4) Loess landform unit classification using deep learning model.

A. Binary terrain segmentation

Some landforms generally exhibit distinct binary topographic characteristics: positive and negative. In loess landforms, positive terrain includes loess tablelands, ridges, and hills, while negative terrain consists of loess gullies. In karst landforms, positive terrain is represented by karst pinnacles, whereas negative terrain comprises karst depressions.

For loess landforms, we first extracted highlands, including loess tablelands, ridges, and hills. Using a 17×17 pixels window, we calculated the difference between the original elevation and the mean elevation within the window. Areas with an elevation difference greater than 20 meters were identified as local highlands. Second, we calculated the surface slope, which was then used as the cost for slope accumulation, with the highlands serving as the source features. Third, positive terrain was extracted from the slope accumulation map using an adaptive threshold, typically defined as the lower quartile of the slope accumulation divided by $\sqrt{2}$ [12]. The remaining areas were classified as negative terrain.

In karst landforms, the idea for distinguishing positive and negative terrain is similar to that of loess landforms. However, the key difference lies in using the drainage network as the source for calculating slope accumulation. We extracted the drainage network from surface flow accumulation using a hydrological analysis method based on DEMs. The negative terrain was extracted, and the remaining areas were positive terrain.

B. Hydrological constrained landform units extraction

Hill peaks are significant topographic features that dominate hills. In the reverse terrain, these peaks are transformed into sinks, representing the lowest points of depressions. When a sink is used as a pour point for watershed calculations, the resulting watershed includes both the hill area and the gently sloping regions surrounding it. By removing these gently sloping regions from the watershed—corresponding to the negative terrain extracted in the previous step, hill ranges, also known as hydrological constrained landform units, can be delineated. The extracted landform units can be regarded as the fundamental objects for landform classification (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Hydrological knowledge-constrained landform units. (a) A single landform unit representing loess hill or an isolated karst Fenglin; (b), (c), (d) and (e) Combination of landform units representing loess tableland, ridge, karst Fengcong and chain Fenglin, respectively

C. Karst landform unit classification using geomorphic rules

Pinnacles with isolated hill shapes are the primary landform elements of karst landscapes, closely resembling the landform units extracted in Fig. 2(a). The diverse spatial combinations of these pinnacles constitute various karst landform entities. For example, pinnacles in Fengcong share a common base rock and are separated by closed depressions, whereas pinnacles in Fenglin are typically isolated or form chain-like structures. Based on these spatial relationships, we classified karst Fenglin and Fengcong using spatial analysis methods [13].

First, we clustered the extracted karst landform units based on the relationship between topographic prominence and maximum relief. Topographic prominence measures the height of a hill's

summit relative to the lowest contour line encircling it but containing no higher summit within it. Next, we defined a "cut rate factor" (c), which quantifies the degree to which the boundary between adjacent pinnacles is eroded by water. This factor reflects whether the pinnacles are located on the same underlying rock base (Fig. 3). Third, we identified the depressions using a hydrological analysis method. Finally, the clustered units that do not intersect any depressions were classified as Fenglin, while those that intersect depressions were classified as Fengcong.

Figure 3. Calculation of the cutting rate factor for karst landform classification.

D. Loess landform unit classification using DL method

Morphologically, loess hills are similar to karst pinnacles, especially in reverse terrain, where both represent depressions. Loess ridges can be viewed as long, linear depressions, while loess tablelands are characterized by a series of depressions with minimal elevation relief. However, the distinction between loess hills and ridges is subtle. To address this, a deep learning model, with its advanced capability to learn complex features from images, was employed to differentiate between them. In this study, we selected 10 areas with typical loess landform characteristics and used DEMs, remotely sensed images, hill-shading map and landform unit samples that we manually delineated to train the deep learning model. All data were resampled to a 10-meter resolution and clipped into 224×224 -pixel patches. We employed a multiscale connected and asymmetric-convolution-based U-Net (MACU-Net) for loess landform classification (Fig. 4), as it has been shown to perform well in multi-target semantic segmentation tasks for high-resolution remotely sensed images [14].

Figure 4. The structure of MACU-Net for loess landform classification.

After optimization, the model was applied to the entire study area to classify loess ridges and loess hills. Each extracted landform unit was classified as either a loess ridge or hill, depending on the proportion of loess hill and ridge areas within it. The negative terrain, as extracted in Section A, was classified as loess gully. Landform units with an average slope less than 5° and an area greater than 0.4 km^2 were classified as loess tablelands.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Extracted landform units

A total of 2,500 karst landform units were extracted and are displayed in Fig. 5(a). The results demonstrate that the extent of karst pinnacles is accurately represented by the extracted landform units. The loess landform units, shown in Fig. 5(b) and 5(c), were found to be located on positive terrain, subdividing the surface into distinct objects. Fig. 5(b) illustrates an area where loess ridges exhibit a narrow, elongated shape, while loess hills are circular in form. These results suggest that the landform units effectively capture the characteristic shapes and distribution of loess and karst features.

Figure 5. Results of landform units. (a) Karst landform units; (b) Loess ridge landform units; (c) Combined loess ridge and hill landform units.

B. Landform classification

The results of loess landform classification were shown in Fig. 6. Fig. 6(a-d) show areas of low relief, dominated by loess gullies and ridge in typical long narrow shape can be obvious observed. Fig. 6(e-g) show loess giant tableland with big size. In mixed loess ridges and hills area, the shape of loess ridges exhibit tree-like form with different structures (Fig. 6(i-l)). Fig. 7 shows the results of the classification of Fenglin and Fengcong. The red areas represent Fengcong, including depressions that are part of Fengcong, shown in dark red. The yellow areas represent Fenglin. A total of 5,000 sample points were selected to assess the classification accuracy of the loess landform through visual interpretation. The classification accuracy of the karst landforms was evaluated by comparing the results with manually delineated boundaries of Fenglin and Fengcong. The classification accuracies for the loess and karst landforms were 94.44% and 82.86%, respectively.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we propose a method for extracting hydrologically constrained landform units from digital elevation models (DEMs). These units serve as fundamental objects for classifying loess and karst landforms. A deep learning method is applied for loess landform classification, while geomorphic rule-based methods are used for karst landforms. The results show that the proposed landform units effectively represent various landform types, including loess tableland, ridge, hill, and karst Fenglin and Fengcong. Comparison with visual interpretation results shows that the classification accuracies for karst and loess landforms are 94.44% and 82.86%, respectively.

Figure 6. Results of loess landform classification.

Figure 7. Results of karst landform classification.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Drăguț L, Eisank C. 2012. Automated object-based classification of topography from SRTM data. *Geomorphology* 141–142: 21–33. DOI: 10.1016/j.geomorph.2011.12.001
- [2] Cao, H., Xiong, L., Wang, H., Zhao, F., & Strobl, J. (2024). Integrating hydrological knowledge into deep learning for DEM super-resolution. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 39(2), 301–325. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13658816.2024.2410345>
- [3] Chen, J., Xiong, L., Tang, G., Hu, G., Wei, H., Zhao, F., & Zhou, L. (2023). Integrating topographic features and patch matching into point cloud restoration for terrain modelling. *International Journal of Digital Earth*, 16(2), 4573–4596. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17538947.2023.2277797>
- [4] Chen, J., Xiong, L., Yin, B., Hu, G., & Tang, G. (2023). Integrating topographic knowledge into point cloud simplification for terrain modelling. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 37(5), 988–1008. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13658816.2023.2180801>
- [5] Wang Y, Chen S-M, Xiong L-Y, Li S-J. 2023. Paleotopography-constrained numerical modeling of loess landform evolution. *Geomorphology* 433: 108725. DOI: 10.1016/j.geomorph.2023.108725
- [6] Nofal R, Abboud IA. 2016. Geomorphological evolution of marine heads on the eastern coast of Red Sea at Saudi Arabian region, using remote sensing techniques. *Arabian Journal of Geosciences* 9: 163. DOI: 10.1007/s12517-015-2234-4
- [7] Huang X, Xiong L, Jiang Y, Li S, Liu K, Ding H, Tang G. 2023. Mapping gully affected areas by using Sentinel 2 imagery and digital elevation model based on the Google Earth Engine. *CATENA* 233: 107473. DOI: 10.1016/j.catena.2023.107473
- [8] Evans IS. 2012. Geomorphometry and landform mapping: What is a landform? *Geomorphology* 137: 94–106. DOI: 10.1016/j.geomorph.2010.09.029
- [9] Fu B, Wang S, Liu Y, Liu J, Liang W, Miao C. 2017. Hydrogeomorphic Ecosystem Responses to Natural and Anthropogenic Changes in the Loess Plateau of China. *Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Sciences* 45: 223–243. DOI: 10.1146/annurev-earth-063016-020552
- [10] Cao M, Tang G, Zhang F, Yang J. 2013. A cellular automata model for simulating the evolution of positive–negative terrains in a small loess watershed. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science* 27: 1349–1363. DOI: 10.1080/13658816.2012.756882
- [11] Hawker L, Uhe P, Paulo L, Sosa J, Savage J, Sampson C, Neal J. 2022. A 30 m global map of elevation with forests and buildings removed. *Environmental Research Letters* 17: 024016. DOI: 10.1088/1748-9326/ac4d4f
- [12] Li S, Yang X, Zhou X, Tang G. 2023. Quantification of Surface Pattern Based on the Binary Terrain Structure in Mountainous Areas. *Remote Sensing* 15: 2664. DOI: 10.3390/rs15102664
- [13] Cao H, Xiong L, Ma J, Wang H, Li S, Yu F, Wang P. 2024. Karst landform classification considering surface flow characteristics derived from digital elevation models. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms* 49: 468–481. DOI: 10.1002/esp.5715
- [14] Li R, Duan C, Zheng S, Zhang C, Atkinson PM. 2022. MACU-Net for Semantic Segmentation of Fine-Resolution Remotely Sensed Images. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters* 19: 1–5. DOI: 10.1109/LGRS.2021.3052886